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Multi-functional shape adaptable composite metamaterials for aerospace applications

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Motivation

Objective:

Stiff yet deformable mechanical metamaterials to enable shape adaptable aerospace structures

Approach:

Novel mechanical metamaterials from thin fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) shells

State-of-the-art:

Anisotropy of FRP not utilized

Current fabrication techniques create weak adhesive bonds where structures fail at low (~10%) global deformation

[1] Bertoldi et al. *Advanced Materials* **22**, 361–366, 2010.

[2] Airoldi et al. *Physica Status Solidi (B) Basic Research*, **252**(7), 1435-1345, 2015.

Polymer material – adaptable but soft

FRP material – Stiff but not adaptable

Thin-shell composite metamaterial concept

- Modified rotating square auxetic mechanism [3]
- Design takes advantage of composite shell mechanics and anisotropy
 - *Bending dominated* deformation to exploit low achievable bending radii
 - High fiber strength and stiffness in axial loading of shells to *improve load carrying capacity*
- Addition of *multi-functional* polymer cores
 - FRP tooling
 - Surfaces for ex. conductive, reflective coatings
 - Can be, optionally, removed after cure

[3] Grima et al. *Journal of Materials Science Letters*, **19**(17), 1563-1565, 2000.

Integral fabrication process

- Entire FRP shell assembly co-cured in single autoclave process without additional adhesive bonds
- Fabrication driven by aerospace requirements
 - *Higher deformation and strength* – elimination of inherently weak bond lines
 - *Mass reduction* – lack of adhesives
 - *Reduced part count and labor times*
- Process description:

Fabricated 5 x 5 metamaterials

- Prototypes made of *ultra-thin 40 gsm prepreg* (M40J carbon fiber with 513 epoxy from NTPT)
- Thickness measurements suggest *sufficient pressure* during cure for most areas (expected thickness of 40 μm)
 - Pressure on outer ligaments and hub/ligament interfaces can be improved

Location	Average Ply Thickness (μm)	Standard deviation (μm)
Ligaments	39	2
Hubs	40	4
Outer ligaments	45	2

[4] North Thin Ply Technologies, "NTPT ThingPreg 513 Data Sheet", product datasheet, available at: www.thinplytechnology.com/assets/mesimages/NTPT-DS-ThinPreg-513-April2017-v3.pdf. 2017.

Measuring metamaterial performance

- Effects of *layup and geometry* on mechanical performance investigated

Sample	Polymer Cores	Ligament Layup	Hub Layup	Ligament Length (mm)
A	No	[0,90,0]	[0,90,0]	30
B	No	[0,90,0]	[0,90,0]	45
C	No	[0,90,0]	[0,90,90,0]	30
D	Yes	[0,90,0]	[0,90,0]	30

- *Uniaxial tensile testing* until metamaterial failure using Zwick Roell testing machine
 - Unconstrained hub rotation and transverse deformation
- Deformation measured using *digital image correlation*
- Elastic performance verified using *finite element simulations* in Abaqus Standard

Representative deformation

10% deformation

20% deformation

40% deformation

Mechanical Response

- Load curve *non-linearity* due to geometry
- Stiffness increase due to cores (sample D) small
 - 3D-printing critical for lightweight cores
- Failure progression
 - *Cracking of single ligament* and stress redistribution
 - Above repeats until no increase in load carrying capacity
 - Ultimate failure via *hinge cracking and delamination* of ligaments from hub
- *Damage tolerant* metamaterial
- Failure due to material strength achieved
- Increasing ligament overlap with hubs delays ultimate failure (sample B)
 - Over 60% global deformation achieved

Conclusion and Outlook

- Novel FRP mechanical metamaterial
 - Redesign for bending dominated deformation
 - Up to 60% global deformation observed
 - Damage tolerance and failure due to material strength
 - Multi-functional surfaces
- Single cure fabrication of complex FRP shell assemblies
 - Reduction of labor time, part counts, and mass
 - Elimination of weak adhesive bonds
 - Incorporation of additive manufacturing ideal for fabrication of complex geometries
- Proposed technique can be applied to arbitrary FRP shell assemblies
- FRP anisotropy can be exploited to further tailor deformation pattern